

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF UTILIZING FOREIGN EXPERIENCES IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM OF UZBEKISTAN AND THE EXPECTED OUTCOMES

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Annotatsiya. *Mazkur maqolada O'zbekistonda oliy ta'lim tizimini sifayti, Finlandiya ta'lim tizimi va Amerika ta'lim tizimlari va O'zbekistonda undan foydalanish istiqbollari haqida fikr yuritiladi.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье предоставляется информация о высшей образовательной системе и ее развитии в Узбекистане, об образовательной системе Финляндии, американских образовательных системах и их преимуществах. В статье также рассматриваются перспективы использования этих систем в Узбекистане.*

Abstract. *This article provides information about the higher education system and its development in Uzbekistan, the education system in Finland, American educational systems, and their advantages. The article also discusses the prospects of using these systems in Uzbekistan.*

Keywords: *Education, modern science, modernization, educational technologies, quality education.*

Introduction

Today, Uzbekistan is becoming a significant player on the global stage. Each sector in the country is being developed uniquely and appropriately, with a constant push for innovation in every field. The issue of advancing the education sector globally is recognized as an important task. Education is considered as the foundation that shapes the spiritual, cultural, social, and economic development of every nation. In the paradigm of education, particular attention is paid to shaping the individual development opportunities for students, fostering their competencies in various subjects, and developing their independence, creativity, entrepreneurship, initiative, and quick adaptability to communication. This requires the implementation of methodological foundations for cultivating scientific thinking in students, starting from the early stages of education, based on a comprehensive approach. Nowadays, significant reforms are being implemented in the field of education. This includes focusing on identifying and developing students' abilities and talents from the initial stages of their education, as well as utilizing international programs and modern pedagogical technologies.

Materials and Methods

Furthermore, organizing a systematic and purposeful activity to enhance students' level of knowledge acquisition is one of the pressing issues of modern times. In this regard, it is of great importance to further expand the pedagogical and methodological possibilities for organizing educational processes that develop students' skills and competencies based on modern foreign and domestic experiences. Defining the priority directions for improving the education system in the Republic of Uzbekistan, raising the quality of higher education, and developing social and economic sectors based on modern science and advanced moral and ethical values are the objectives of the "Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" approved by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, by the decree PF-5847 dated October 8, 2019. The expected results from this concept include the development of public-private partnerships in the field of higher education, ensuring

that the level of higher education exceeds 50% through the establishment of state and non-state higher education institutions, and creating a competitive environment in the field.

Result and discussion

The organized and systematic implementation of activities aimed at improving students' knowledge acquisition through a purposeful approach is one of the urgent tasks of modern times. Accordingly, it is crucial to expand the pedagogical and methodological possibilities of organizing educational processes that develop students' skills and competencies based on modern foreign and domestic experiences. Defining the priority directions for improving the education system in the Republic of Uzbekistan, raising the quality of higher education, and developing social and economic sectors based on modern science and advanced moral and ethical values are the objectives of the "Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" approved by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, by the decree PF-5847 dated October 8, 2019. The expected results from this concept include the development of public-private partnerships in the field of higher education, ensuring that the level of higher education exceeds 50% through the establishment of state and non-state higher education institutions, and creating a competitive environment in the field.

Education is the most transformative process in the world, shaping not only individuals but also society. Regardless of where we are in the world, we need to pay attention to primary education because education helps us gain new knowledge, think critically, progress in life, and understand the world. Education exists in all countries and is evolving with new initiatives in today's developed countries. Let's take Finland's education system, which excels in educational standards, as an example. Finland is different from other countries in terms of its education system. The basic education law in Finland (1998) outlines three main objectives for Finnish education:

- 1) To provide students with the knowledge and skills they need in life.
- 2) To promote development and equality in society.
- 3) To ensure equality in education across the country.

Finland's population currently stands at 5.5 million, and approximately 560,500 students are studying in 2,341 public schools. Schools typically hold lessons five days per week. All of the schools are at the same level, and students are divided into different classes or specialized educational institutions according to their abilities. Finland's education system is based on seven principles that can be summarized as follows: Equality - All Finnish schools offer the same education to students regardless of their background or location. Free education - Students are given all the necessary materials and equipment for free. Individuality - Teachers and students who are finding it difficult to adapt to the lessons are given specialized attention and support. The Finnish education system does not practice streaming students to additional classes. Practicality - Students are prepared for life, not just exams. They participate in practical work such as using a credit card, creating contracts, setting up websites, building, cooking, marketing, etc. Trust and respect - Teachers are highly respected and considered to be masters of their craft, who are entrusted to deliver quality teaching. Independence - Teachers guide students to learn as they wish and encourage them to apply what they have learned in practical situations. The knowledge of how to apply knowledge in real-life situations is shaped by practical exercises. The interests and opinions of students are taken into consideration and reinforced. In addition to this, the high literacy culture inherent in Finnish society also directly impacts the success of Finnish students. In conclusion, the success of Finland's education system is closely linked to Finnish values and culture. We must learn from this and adapt essential aspects of the Finnish education system to our

education system. Like Finland, the United States is one of the leading countries in the world for higher education. Their higher education system boasts quality education, renowned professors, as well as state-of-the-art infrastructure and facilities. American universities offer over two million courses to students. The education system in the USA covers primary, secondary, and higher education. Higher education in the USA is divided into four grades: associate, bachelor's, master's, and doctorate. The US follows a credit system where 30 credits are required to complete a program. The teaching methods used in American schools may differ from other countries because they focus on practical knowledge more than theoretical knowledge. Additionally, obtaining an education in the USA is more expensive than in most countries, mainly because of the excellent quality of education from which they benefit. The United States of America realizes about 99% of its citizens are high school graduates by law. The law applies to every citizen from the age of six to eight years old.

Conclusion

In summary, the advantages of the education system in the USA lie in the diversity of its students, the varying requirements of the education system, and the compatibility between theoretical knowledge and practical application, as well as the renowned universities worldwide. To put it simply, the education systems of the United States and Finland have both been offering exceptional education to their students for many years, and they have been contributing to their students' achieving high results in international assessment programs. Finland ranks second in the world in terms of natural sciences and fifth in mathematics, preparing its students for real life, not just exams. We have chosen the former as an example of the best in Finnish education. The use of modern technology in the American education system has been awakening the curiosity of many teachers worldwide, highlighting the need for them to learn and implement it in practice.

REFERENCES

1. Decision on the Approval of the Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, PF-5847, dated October 8, 2019.
2. S. Sulaymonova, "Development of Ecological Awareness in Primary School Students Based on Animation Techniques" PhD Abstract - Namangan. 2022.
3. Azimaxon Kamolova, "The Scientific and Theoretical Foundations of Studying the Sources of Popular Pedagogy in Educating the Younger Generation" in "Science and Education" Scientific Journal / Impact Factor 3.567 (SJIF), December 2022, Volume 3 Issue 12, pages 590-592.